

DEVELOPING PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR INCREASING ENTREPRENEURIAL SKILLS IN STUDENTS BASED ON LEARNING OUTCOMES

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Abstract. *The results of vocational education in the formation of entrepreneurial skills in students are one of the important directions that serve to train potential personnel for the economy of our country, ensure the employment of vocational education students in the form of entrepreneurship, and train qualified specialists in society. The spiritual and educational political and legal foundations of directing young students to entrepreneurship are often determined by laws and regulatory documents with specific mechanisms. These documents cover the requirements for entrepreneurial education, the rights of young students to acquire a profession, and the support provided to students by the state. In our country, in international programs for determining the literacy and qualifications of students and monitoring the quality of education, improving the quality of teaching in specific subjects, improving their theoretical, methodological and methodological foundations, and assessing the level of independent mastery of knowledge are defined as separate parameters. The reforms being implemented in the context of active innovation processes in the socio-economic spheres of our society have put on the agenda one of the main areas of development of the education system - the problem of forming and improving entrepreneurial intellectual qualities in students of vocational and technical colleges.*

Keywords: *competence, intellectual, entrepreneurship, global demand and competitiveness, dual education, labor market in the world and in our country, profession, innovative projects, new startups.*

Introduction. In today's rapidly changing labor market, guiding students to entrepreneurship is a requirement of the times, taking into account the interests and abilities of children, and directing them to the correct and targeted choice of entrepreneurial skills. This process is of great importance not only in determining the future of vocational education students, but also in developing our economy in a specific mechanism. It is important to provide students with the necessary information and skills in choosing an entrepreneurial direction, as well as in exploring their personal interests and talents and dual education. Such an approach will become the foundation for training successful specialists in the future.

The adoption of the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to attract young people to entrepreneurship and support their business initiatives", and the fact that all "Business Fundamentals" teachers in the regions are being trained by specialists from Germany in order to ensure the implementation of this Resolution, are evidence of the serious attention our government is paying to this issue. At this point, it is important to be able to distinguish between the concepts of entrepreneurship and business: Entrepreneurship (entrepreneurial activity, this is business) is an independent activity carried out on a risk-based basis, aimed at regularly obtaining income from owning property, selling goods, or providing

services. Entrepreneurial activity (entrepreneurship) is an initiative activity carried out by business entities in accordance with the law, aimed at obtaining income (profit) at their own risk and under their own property responsibility.

2. Proposals for solving these problems

The following proposals can be put forward to solve the above problems. The following are proposed as solutions: It is advisable to introduce an educational organization consultant responsible for guiding students in the formation of entrepreneurial skills in almost every district or city, where there are colleges, vocational schools, and technical schools. It would be advisable for the consultants of this educational organization to carry out promotional work in each educational organization or neighborhood, in collaboration with activists, on the formation of new entrepreneurial skills that will enter the labor market in the future. The demand for labor resources in the global market is changing dramatically. Currently, the need for specialists in such areas as robotics, artificial intelligence, biotechnology, digital marketing, and creative industries is increasing. Therefore, targeted training of young people in these areas is of great importance. Fundamental measures must be taken to ensure that the Uzbek education system adapts to these changes. Depending on the purpose, type and direction of entrepreneurship, it can be divided into production, commercial and consulting types. These are also divided into their own types.

According to Article 5 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Entrepreneurship", there are the following types of entrepreneurs:

- Individual entrepreneurship;
- Private entrepreneurship;
- Collective entrepreneurship;
- Mixed entrepreneurship.

In order to use the entrepreneurial form in students, various meetings, master classes, business trainings with large entrepreneurs and business owners in vocational education are considered the main source of forming entrepreneurial skills in students. Unfortunately, these situations do not occur in practice, and students are aware of their shortcomings.

The high attention paid to the education sector in our country is of great importance for the all-round development of our youth. Today, all the necessary conditions have been created for our youth to receive thorough education, fully master a certain field, and take a worthy place in society. The vocational education agency plays a significant role in meeting the educational needs of the individual, society, and the state, and it carries out a wide range of training of specialists in both technical and social fields.

Therefore, the main goal of the vocational education system is to prepare competitive personnel for the needs of the labor market, including small businesses and private entrepreneurship, through the introduction of dual education and vocational training stages, and to meet the needs of people of different ages for education based on the principle of "Lifelong Learning".

The development of society, economy and information technologies requires the expansion of the functions of a secondary vocational education specialist in colleges and technical schools, such as administrative and technical support of management processes, direct management of technical, technological and information systems, monitoring the quality of producIn order to increase the growing role of human capital in the economic and social development of our country, to provide the processes of forming a market economy with qualified personnel in order to

introduce innovations, the latest achievements of science and technology, and modern technologies, great attention is being paid to the development of proposals for improving the system of training specialists for various sectors of the economy, including entrepreneurship, taking into account the plans assigned to the education system, especially the vocational education system. Entrepreneurship is not only an area that demonstrates the active potential of young people, but also one of the main sources of job creation for consumers and their environmental properties, and ensuring their safety.

One of the pressing problems of vocational education institutions is ensuring the employment of college and technical school students, their placement in jobs in their majors. After all, 19.6 million or 55 percent of our country's population is made up of young people and children under the age of 30. Today's youth are the creators of our tomorrow, our future; entrepreneurial activity, which forms the basis of a market economy, by its very nature requires risk-taking, mobility, and entrepreneurial qualities, most of which are often embodied in young people. In the formation of entrepreneurial skills of students of vocational colleges, technical schools and vocational schools, we can say that only the integration of cognitive activity and entrepreneurial theory, which allows for the formation of entrepreneurial thinking, which is considered the basis for the formation of entrepreneurial skills, as well as the practical orientation of the formation of entrepreneurial literacy, can provide the opportunity for more effective professional socialization of graduating students. The success of professional adaptation, socialization, and competitiveness of students of such educational institutions is associated with the level of their preparation for activity in the formation of entrepreneurial skills. Today, attention should be paid to the formation of entrepreneurial competence in students studying all entrepreneurial disciplines, which will ensure the adaptation of graduates and their self-employment in the labor market, as well as the innovativeness and effectiveness of entrepreneurial and professional knowledge and skills in the process of establishing their own business activities.

It is intended to be used in the preparation and conduct of lectures and practical exercises in such educational institutions. In college and technical schools, students first study professional subjects when preparing for professional activity. In the lower courses, they are not yet familiar with methodological subjects and have only a superficial idea of professional activity. In the senior years, students are involved in directly mastering the elements of professional activity through training in the theory and methodology of teaching, studying professional disciplines and special disciplines, pedagogical practice, and completing coursework and graduation qualification work. The creation of a modern educational and material base is an important pedagogical condition for preparing students for professional activity. Based on the study of students' practice, I came to the conclusion that the system of knowledge and skills acquired in vocational education using modern educational and didactic tools is not used to solve professional problems. The activity of a teacher who has sufficient training in the field of ICT is of a reproductive nature. An analysis of the reasons for this led to the conclusion that the accumulated experience of teachers of educational institutions in using modern educational didactic tools in their teaching activities is often not in demand, since many college and technical school graduates have not formed the motivation for continuous learning and application in practice.

In recent years, simulation technologies in medical education have become one of the main methods for mastering clinical skills. Modern requirements require the implementation of more effective forms of medical care. The need to provide high-quality medical care to the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan, including children, has led to an increase in demand for simulation

technologies. Simulation includes a complex of measures aimed at developing practical skills, algorithms and communication. The goal of the project is to improve simulation teaching methods, increase teaching efficiency, and analyze difficulties in the teaching process to develop professional skills in students. To achieve this goal, the following tasks must be performed:

Formation of students' practical skills through the introduction of simulation educational technologies into the teaching process.

Development of stress resistance and quick decision-making skills in students.

Identification and analysis of key indicators of increasing teaching efficiency through simulation technologies.

Simulation is about studying the challenges encountered in the process of improving education and finding solutions to them.

"Darya" is the European Union's first regional initiative on vocational education in Central Asia. The project will be implemented in cooperation with the regional countries' vocational education and employment authorities, think tanks and other social institutions during 2022-2027. As is known, during the pandemic, young people in Central Asia, like all over the world, faced difficulties in improving their professional skills. The project, worth 5 million euros, will pay special attention to the integration of young people into the labor market and improving their skills. The project, which is planned for 2022-2027, is being implemented by the European Union. The European Union Coordinator for Central Asia is Ms. Christine Hemsheimer. These projects are of regional importance and consist of several modules aimed at improving professional education, inclusive education, and vocational training in the countries of Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, and Kyrgyzstan. One of these modules is "Scaffold". "Scaffold" is a set of cards for teachers in the formal and non-formal education sectors who want to design learning activities that help develop digital, entrepreneurial, personal, social, educational, and sustainability competencies. It helps teachers design learning activities for students that incorporate several key competencies and support their development.

The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 5, 2018 No. PQ-3775 "On additional measures to improve the quality of education in higher educational institutions and ensure their active participation in the comprehensive reforms being implemented in the country" sets out issues such as harmonizing the assessment system and criteria with the stages of the continuing education system, introducing modern, transparent and fair methods of assessing student knowledge (automated, portfolio, test tests, creative work, anti-plagiarism, etc.), taking into account the specifics of educational areas, including a system that excludes the participation of a teacher who taught a particular subject in the final control processes.

Assessment of the development of specialized disciplines in the preparation of future engineers for professional activity in vocational educational institutions is a multifaceted process that includes various pedagogical, technical and competency-based approaches. Because the inconsistency of the content of general professional disciplines such as "Technical Mechanics" creates the problem of standardizing the assessment of specialized disciplines. This variability affects the uniformity of professional qualifications of engineering graduates and indicates the need for a more systematic approach to the development and assessment of curricula.

In order to ensure the continuous development of professional competencies in our republic, it is important to develop models that can be adapted for engineering education. Analysis of the competencies formed in future engineers is of great importance for solving professional

problems of fundamental knowledge in mathematics and natural laws. This fundamental knowledge is very important for future engineers to effectively master specialized disciplines.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, we can say that in the training of qualified specialists in the petrochemical industry, it is important to deeply understand these aspects and integrate them into educational programs. It is also very important to develop new assessment methods and optimal systems, adhere to international standards, and automate education in order to achieve efficiency in assessing the results of mastering future engineers in teaching specialized disciplines. It can be said that today, the service and manufacturing sectors are the drivers of the economy. The professional approach of the personnel working in these sectors to the sector leads to economic development. However, the fact that most service and manufacturing sectors are staffed by personnel who have not studied in this direction and have not mastered advanced foreign experience is an obstacle to the development of the sector. Today, in order to support young people, our government is creating a number of benefits for all young people, including middle-level sector representatives, to contribute to economic development by becoming self-employed in their respective sectors.

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